
Cybersecurity Threats and Mitigation Strategies in E-Procurement Systems: A Case Study of A Local Government (Public Sector)

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ABSTRACT: Technological advancement has undoubtedly impacted humanity in different ways influencing the way things are done. This has informed the transition of the traditional manual procurement processes to the internet-enabled e-procurement systems which is fast gaining popularity and acceptance across the globe because of the enormous benefits therein. However, cybercriminals, taking advantage of the technology, have become more sophisticated in their antics thereby necessitating the need for the study into the cybersecurity and mitigation methods to make e-procurement systems secured for safe use. This has become pertinent as there have been cyber incident(s) in the public sector service industry that had raised concerns regarding the continued use of e-procurement systems. Especially so because there is not much research in this subject area to give more practical insights in Nigeria and Sub-Saharan African countries.

The research was carried out using the questionnaire designed using the cloud-based JISC Online Surveys to elicit objective data from experienced professionals while two key and strategic professionals were interviewed to harvest accurate and adequate information regarding the implementation of e-procurement systems and the related data security issues. The combination of quantitative data from the questionnaires and the qualitative data from the interview made it possible to gather all relevant data that might be overlooked if only one method was used.

It has been confirmed through this study that pre-engagement security checks on personnel is imperative to reduce the possibility of insider attacks and that organizational policies are needed regarding incident response, the use of peripherals and personal devices within the organization, the regular backup policy and consistent update of Disaster Recovery Plans. Also important is regular personnel capacity building to keep them up to date, especially in security awareness to build a security culture across organizations. Furthermore, it has been confirmed that appropriately configured firewalls (hardware and / or software) would shield an application (website), organizational systems and networks from the DDoS attacks; the introduction of role-based access control in an application will prevent the possibility of unauthorized access to system resources through escalation of user privileges; finally when properly configured, an application can prevent SQLi attack through input validation which can be enhanced to prevent brute force attack; and when strong identification authentication is used, it would be difficult for cybercriminals to successfully use stolen login details to gain unauthorized access to systems or applications. All re-affirming that security must be built into every application (e-procurement) from the design phase to achieve the security goals of confidentiality, integrity, and availability.

KEYWORDS: Cybersecurity, E-Procurement, SQL Injection, DDoS, Public Sector, Risk Mitigation

1. INTRODUCTION:

E-procurement offers organizations worldwide increased efficiency and access to global markets through digitized procurement processes (bidding, evaluation, contracting, payments) (Girgvlani, 2023; Charnor & Quartey, 2024). Its rapid adoption is driven by cost savings and benefits like streamlined processes, efficiency and improved transparency (Abache, 2022). However, cybersecurity threats, particularly in developing economies, create scepticism (Droppe, 2023). Limited research in Nigeria and Sub-Saharan Africa into the implementation of E-procurement systems necessitated this research that is aimed at solving challenges faced by a local government (public sector) referred to as SakovicCorp (Mohungoo, Brown, & Kabanda, 2020), (Abdullahi, Oyewobi, Ganiyu, & Shittu, 2021), (Oseni, 2024).

This study used questionnaires and focus groups to explore cybersecurity issues in e-procurement, identify mitigation strategies, and determine critical success factors for secure system design. Specifically, it focuses on preventing SQL injection attacks (a top OWASP threat) (OWASP, 2025) within a Nigerian public sector's (SakovicCorp's) e-procurement database, addressing challenges that have stalled e-procurement adoption despite its potential. The study also examines DDoS attack mitigation and other success factors for e-procurement implementation.

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The World Bank emphasizes public procurement's importance to national economies, highlighting the need to address challenges like data breaches, which have risen sharply with e-procurement adoption (Oshoma, Raji, & Yusuf, 2024), (WEF, 2025), (WorldBank, 2025). The fact that these systems handle sensitive data increases the risk of significant losses (UNDP, 2024). In addition, fraud is rampant in public procurement, particularly in developing economies (Iwerebor, et al., 2024; Charnor & Quartey, 2024) thereby fuelling resistance to the adoption of E-Procurement (Egwim, Dike, & Nmecha, 2024). Furthermore, cyberattacks, including DDoS attacks and website disruptions, further threaten e-procurement (Issabayeva, Yesseniyazova, & Grega, 2019), (PYMNTS, 2019), (Droppe, 2023). The Global Cybersecurity Outlook 2025 indicate a surge in attacks (WEF, 2025), necessitating proactive security measures and user training (Turyatamba & Turyasingura, 2024). Given that human error contributes to over 90% of breaches (Thakur, Barker, & Ali, 2024), (Tikanmäki & Ruoslahti, 2024) such trainings are crucial (Moh, 2025).

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

This literature review examines cybersecurity issues and mitigation strategies for e-procurement systems, aiming to inform the development of a secure system for a developing country's public sector, comparable to those in advanced nations. E-procurement, facilitated by growing global internet access of 67.9% in 2025 (Statista, 2025) and 115% increase in internet users in Sub-Saharan Africa from 2016 to 2021 (WorldBank, 2024) offers numerous benefits like expanded market access, efficiency, and transparency, contributing to economic growth (Stephens & Valverde, 2018), (Masudin, Aprilia, Nugraha, & Restuputri, 2021), (Sánchez-Rodríguez, Martínez-Lorente, & Hemsworth, 2020), (Kemp, 2021), (Abache, 2022; Egwim, Dike, & Nmecha, 2024). However, sophisticated cybercrime poses a significant threat, causing substantial financial losses (Hurst, 2021), (WEF, 2025).

E-procurement offers benefits like reduced overhead and wider product access (Sánchez-Rodríguez, Martínez-Lorente, & Hemsworth, 2020), (Gadour, 2024), (Egwim, Dike, & Nmecha, 2024), but cybersecurity concerns hinder adoption, especially in public sectors (Inusah, Kazaz, & Ulubeyli, 2025), (Droppe, 2023). Furthermore, as reported by Inusah et al. (2025), implementation challenges include low leadership commitment, poor funding, inadequate resources, data breaches, and outdated technology (Naeem, 2021), (Mohungoo, Brown, & Kabanda, 2020), (Naeem, Sulaimani, & Anwar, 2021), (WorldBank, 2024). Additionally, the increase in the frequency and sophistication of cyberattacks is also a factor (Rowell, 2021), (Inusah, Kazaz, & Ulubeyli, 2025), (WEF, 2025).

E-Procurement Systems and Cybersecurity: Cybersecurity protects digital assets from unauthorized access and corruption (Inusah, Kazaz, & Ulubeyli, 2025), (IBM, 2021), (Turyatamba & Turyasingura, 2024). Notwithstanding, cybersecurity concerns impede e-procurement adoption (Mohungoo, Brown, & Kabanda, 2020) due to the valuable data stored, making these systems attractive targets. Furthermore, the ever-increasing data breaches has continued to fuel these concerns (Alex, 2021), (Kerner, 2025), (WEF, 2025).

Therefore, there is a need to adopt appropriate mitigation strategies such as input validation, cryptography, authentication, access control, adoption of multi-factor authentication (MFA), biometrics, data masking, encryption, and tokenization (Kilincer, Ertam, & Sengur, 2021), (Looker, 2021), (Inusah, Kazaz, & Ulubeyli, 2025). These should be integrated from the design phase for effective and efficient security (Chapple, Stewart, & Gibson, 2021). Additionally, blockchain and AI offer further protection (Okon, et al., 2024), (Banafa, 2019), (Gunasekara, Sridarran, & Rajaratnam, 2021), (Girgvliani, 2023). It is noteworthy that training and capacity building are crucial (UNDP, 2024), (Moh, 2025), given that over 90% of cyberattacks are attributed to human errors (Thakur, Barker, & Ali, 2024), (Tikanmäki & Ruoslahti, 2024), (Omweri, 2024).

Approaches to Cybersecurity: Key cybersecurity approaches include: Access Control (RBAC, MAC, DAC) (Chapple, Stewart, & Gibson, 2021), (University of Hawai'i, 2021), (Martin, 2019), (Lashkov, 2018); Identity and Authentication, Cryptography, Firewalls and Data Masking (Islam, 2024), (Chapple, Stewart, & Gibson, 2021), (National Cyber Security Centre, 2018), (Weisman, 2021), (Qiu, Gui, & Zhao, 2020).

Regulations on Data Protection: Data protection regulations, like the UK's Data Protection Act 2018 (based on GDPR) and Nigeria's Data Protection Regulation (NDPR) (NITDA, 2019), mandate security measures to prevent unauthorized data access. Compliance requires integrating these measures into e-procurement systems from the design stage (GOV.UK, 2018).

E-Procurement Systems and Cyberattacks: E-procurement systems are attractive targets due to the valuable data they handle (bank details, IP, bid data). Common attacks include DDoS, SQL injection (SQLi), ransomware, man-in-the-middle, and supply chain attacks (PYMNTS, 2019), (Droppe, 2023).

Prevention of SQLi Attack: SQLi, a top OWASP threat, allows attackers to access sensitive data (OWASP, 2025), (Alenezi, Nadeem, & Asif, 2021). Protecting against SQLi requires robust security practices implemented from the design phase (Chapple, Stewart, & Gibson, 2021), (Kaur & Kaur, 2014). Mitigation strategies include input validation, Web Application Firewalls (WAFs),

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regular software updates, principle of least privilege, prepared statements / stored procedures, and whitelisting / blacklisting (UC Berkeley, 2025), (Alenezi, Nadeem, & Asif, 2021), (Chapple, Stewart, & Gibson, 2021).

Countermeasures of DDoS Attacks: A Distributed Denial-of-Service (DDoS) attack prevents authorised users from accessing a system by flooding it with traffic from several compromised devices (bots) (Cloudflare, 2025), (Silva, 2021). When directed by the attacker, these bots, which are managed by a command-and-control server, produce enormous amounts of bandwidth. However, DDoS mitigation requires differentiating legitimate from malicious traffic, a complex task (Cloudflare, 2025). Therefore, a layered approach is recommended, including: blackhole routing; rate limiting; firewall/router configuration; Anycast network diffusion (often outsourced); ISP rerouting (Ferrillo, 2016), (Weisman, 2021A); network redundancy (Irwin, 2020), (Isberto, 2021) hybrid IDPS (Shah, Khan, & Ahmad, 2021), (Weisman, 2021); honeypots (Santhosh, 2024); and specialized hardware (Gartner, 2025).

E-Procurement Systems in the Public Sector: E-procurement offers significant benefits to the public sector (government and publicly funded services) (Ebong, 2020), (Egwim, Dike, & Nmecha, 2024), (Inusah, Kazaz, & Ulubeyli, 2025) particularly in developing economies, where it can combat corruption, increase transparency, and improve value for money (Gadour, 2024), (Fourie & Malan, 2021), (Turyatamba & Turyasingura, 2024). E-procurement training for public sector staff is essential due to the substantial procurement budgets (Turyatamba & Turyasingura, 2024), (Boafo, Ahudey, & Darteh, 2020), (Ebong, 2020). Although successful in developed nations, public sector e-procurement adoption lags in many developing economies, including Nigeria (Mohungoo, Brown, & Kabanda, 2020).

Critical Success Factors for the Implementation of E-Procurement: E-procurement adoption, like other E-governance strategies, hinges on technology (tools, funding, security, legal framework) (Moh, 2025), human behaviour (acceptance, skills) (Egwim, Dike, & Nmecha, 2024), and organizational factors (structure, size) (Gunasekaran, McGaughey, Ngai, & Rai, 2009). Larger, centralized organizations are more likely to implement e-procurement due to availability of the required resources (Issah, David, & Eric, 2024). However, human resistance, especially from management, and inadequate staff skills are major obstacles (Shakya, 2024), (MavenVista, 2024), (Lakhani, 2020), (Abache, 2022).

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This research investigates e-procurement data security, cyberattack dynamics, mitigation, and critical success factors to develop a secure system for a Nigerian public sector service industry. Data was collected via questionnaires from public sector professionals in Nigeria and the UK, and from professionals in financial institutions, private sector, and non-profit organizations. Analysis will inform security measures for an agile software development approach (Hoda, Salleh, & Grundy, 2018), (Chapple, Stewart, & Gibson, 2021). A systematic approach is essential for valid research (Saunders, Lewis, & Thornhill, 2012).

Research Philosophy: This research uses a mixed-methods approach, combining positivism (objective, empirical observation via questionnaires) and interpretivism (subjective interpretation via interviews) (Saunders M. , 2009), (Ryan, 2018), (Serva & Chapel, 2015), (BRM, 2021), (Žukauskas, Vveinhardt, & Andriukaitienė, 2018). This approach aims for accurate data on e-procurement security and answers the research questions while minimizing subjectivity.

Research Design: This mixed-methods research design used a literature review, expert interviews, and questionnaires to gather data on e-procurement data security in a public sector service industry. Data was analysed using JISC. This design captures both objective and subjective perspectives for a comprehensive understanding (Mitchell, 2018), (Maarouf, 2019), (Khatri, 2020).

Research Strategy: This research focuses on designing a secure e-procurement application for SAKOVIC Corporation, a public sector service industry, hardened against SQL injection (a top OWASP threat) (Alenezi, Nadeem, & Asif, 2021), (Tsing, 2019), (Chapple, Stewart, & Gibson, 2021). Data was gathered from procurement and IT professionals. The application was developed using ASP.NET Core in C# (Microsoft, 2021) with SSL/TLS, input validation (Roth, Anderson, & Luttin, 2020), (Microsoft, 2021), JavaScript (Toledo, 2018), (Achary, 2018), and Bootstrap (Berezhnoi, 2019), (Keller, 2019). Two-factor authentication and RBAC were implemented.

Data Collection and JISC Software: Data was collected via a JISC-based questionnaire, focusing on e-procurement systems, cybersecurity, and mitigation methods. Data handling complied with the Data Protection Act 2018/GDPR (Proton Technologies AG, 2021), (Hoofnagle, Slood, & Borgesius, 2019), (GOV.UK, 2018). JISC facilitated quantitative data collection and analysis. Qualitative data was collected through focus group interviews. Respondents were primarily Nigerian (81.1%), with most having at least a bachelor's degree (94.6%), aged 31+, and male (70.3%). The majority worked in the public sector (67.1%).

4. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

This research revealed key e-procurement implementation challenges, particularly in cybersecurity. While 65.7% of respondents have adopted e-procurement, process-related constraints include inadequate IT infrastructure (42.6%), internet issues (17%), and

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lack of qualified personnel (17.7%). Administrative constraints include lack of management support (24.1%), inadequate policies (27.7%), lack of policy implementation (14.6%), funding issues (10.2%), and security concerns (23.4%). Governments and top management's commitment is crucial for secure e-procurement implementation (Omweri, 2024), (Moh, 2025).

While 91.7% acknowledge e-procurement's potential to curb unethical behaviour, only 69% have experienced it, raising questions about ongoing practices and measurement challenges that might require further study (Schøll & Ubaydi, 2017). Furthermore, despite cybersecurity measures, human capacity building is essential, as human error contributes to over 90% of breaches (Thakur, Barker, & Ali, 2024), (Tikanmäki & Ruoslahti, 2024). Pre-employment security checks are important, but the 11% who don't conduct them pose a risk. While 76.8% have some form of disaster recovery plan (DRP) or backup, 23.2% lack a DRP, highlighting a vulnerability. Cyberattack prevention requires a comprehensive approach from management to all personnel. Strong policies and enforcement are essential.

In summary, the research identified SQLi attacks and DDoS as primary threats to e-procurement systems. Key mitigation strategies include:

- **Enforcing input validation and prepared statements:** Preventing SQLi attacks by sanitizing user inputs.
- **Deploying robust authentication mechanisms:** MFA and role-based access control minimize unauthorized access.
- **Implementing network security measures:** Firewalls, Intrusion Detection and Prevention Systems (IDPS), and load balancing reduce the risk of DDoS attacks.
- **Regular security training:** Increasing staff awareness to mitigate risks related to human error.

5. FUTURE WORK

This study has identified several areas for further research:

- a. A significant drop from 91.7% to 69% was observed when respondents compared the expected benefits of e-procurement in reducing fraud to their personal experiences. This raises questions about whether unethical practices persist, the effectiveness of e-procurement in curbing corruption, or the complexity of fraud measurement.
- b. E-procurement adoption appears higher in the public sector (67.3%) than in the private sector (53.9%). Further research is needed to verify this and explore possible reasons.
- c. Automating the verification of registration evidence through integration with registration authorities could improve efficiency. Investigating its feasibility and reliability is essential.

6. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The recommendations for secure e-procurement implementation, especially in developing nations, fall into three categories: human resources, technology, and workload influence.

Human Resources: Top management buy-in is crucial, requiring clear communication of e-procurement benefits. Thorough pre-engagement security checks are essential, especially for SoC personnel. Strict access control protocols, based on least privilege, must be enforced. Continuous personnel capacity building, including security awareness training, is vital.

Technology: Cybersecurity should be integrated into e-procurement systems from the design phase. Real-time incident response features, such as honeypots and automated alerts, are recommended. Comprehensive activity logging is needed for audit trails and accountability. Other crucial security measures include firewalls, input validation, role-based access control, data masking, encryption, tokenization and multi-factor authentication.

Workload Influence: Public sector e-procurement adoption offers numerous benefits: access to global markets, reduced turnaround time and paperwork, improved monitoring and evaluation, better inventory control, and fraud/corruption prevention. Centralized coordination of e-procurement deployment, including capacity building, ensures standardized service delivery.

In conclusion, the study reaffirms the importance of integrating security measures into e-procurement systems from the design phase. Public sector organizations must adopt a proactive approach by implementing multi-layered security controls, conducting regular vulnerability assessments, and enforcing compliance with data protection regulations. Future research should explore AI-driven security enhancements to strengthen e-procurement resilience against emerging threats.

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Appendix 1: Ethics Declaration Form

Ethics Declaration Form

Computing & Technology Ethical Issues Declaration Form

All project students are required to consider potential ethical issues that may arise over the course of their project work. A discussion regarding ethics relating to your project must be held with your supervisor and any potential ethical issues identified. In order to allow effective monitoring and record keeping, this ethical declaration must be completed for every project and signed by both the student and supervisor, whether or not ethical issues were considered to be involved. No student can commence work unless this form has been completed.

Ethical Approval
Project work using human volunteers as subjects requires ethical approval, examples might include: monitoring subjects physiological and biomechanical responses to stimulus, undergoing psychological tests, examining the impact of applications on human behaviour, conducting any work with participants classed as vulnerable (e.g. minors), utilising any data collection methods that seek personal or confidential information. If your project produces any ethical issues as described above an application for ethical approval must be made to the Colleges Non-Invasive Ethical Committee. If the work appears to be of a more sensitive nature, approval may be required through the Universities Ethical Review Committee; discuss with your supervisor or module leader if in doubt.

Student Name: STEPHEN ADENIYI SOBULO **Student Number:** N0907277

Course: MSC IT SECURITY SW

Project Title: A Systematic Approach to Data Security on E-Procurement Systems: A Case Study of SME in Service Industry

Name of Supervisor: DR. FUNMINIYI OLAJIDE

I have read the above text and discussed this with my supervisor? Yes No

This project requires:

Approval from the Non-Invasive Ethical Committee	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
Approval from the Universities Ethical Review Committee	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
Disclosure and Barring Service (DBS) approval	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
A Health and Safety Risk assessment	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No

Please give details below
The research will be developed to create educational information that would be able to provide solution to how a successful e-procurement system can be developed and implemented using agile technology. The system development life cycle (SDLC) method that focuses on adaptive and predictive approach will be explored.
The research has no ethical consideration. It would focus on primary and secondary data sources including the framework approach and security consideration in e-procurement systems in the SME service industry in a developing economy.

Signature of student:

Signature of Supervisor: 03 June 2021